

Psychiatric Comorbidities, Pathway of Care & Follow-Up after Therapeutic Interventions in Substance Use Disorder

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Abstract:

This prospective longitudinal study examines the prevalence and patterns of psychiatric comorbidities among 100 male patients with substance use disorder (SUD) at SCB Medical College, Odisha. Using the MINI International Neuropsychiatric Interview (DSM-5 Version 7.0.2), patients aged 18-60 years were assessed for dual diagnosis over a one-year period. Results indicate a high prevalence (77%) of dual diagnosis, predominantly involving psychotic and mood disorders alongside SUD. Cannabis and alcohol were the most common substances used. Sociodemographically, patients were primarily young, Hindu, and from lower socioeconomic backgrounds. Initial care pathways often involved consultation with medical practitioners or faith healers. Follow-up assessments at 3, 6, and 12 months showed significant improvement in both groups, emphasizing the need for integrated treatment approaches to enhance long-term outcomes.

Keywords: Substance Use Disorder, Dual Diagnosis, Psychiatric Comorbidities, Integrated Treatment, MINI International Neuropsychiatric Interview, Sociodemographic Factors.

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Introduction

Substance use disorders (SUDs) are chronic, relapsing health conditions influenced by complex bio psychosocial factors [1] (UNGASS & UNODC, 2016; UNODC, 2015, 2018, 2021). According to the DSM-V, SUDs are characterized by a problematic pattern of substance use causing significant impairment and distress, diagnosed when specific criteria are met within a 12-month period.

Comorbidity, or the co-occurrence of distinct clinical conditions, significantly impacts prognosis and treatment [4] (Feinstein, 1970; Santucci & Ross, 2013). Dual diagnosis, where SUDs coexist with other psychiatric disorders, necessitates integrated treatment approaches.

Prevalence of dual diagnosis varies: Indian clinic-based studies report rates from 16.4% to 75% (Trivedi et al., 1978; Goswami et al., 2003; Basu et al., 2013), European studies show 19%-35% (Carrà et al., 2012), and over 60% in adolescents (Hser et

al., 2001). High comorbidity rates are observed with anxiety, depression, bipolar disorder, ADHD, psychotic disorders, and personality disorders (Magidson et al., 2012; Conway et al., 2006; De Alwis et al., 2014; Lubman et al., 2010).

Additionally, 25% of individuals with serious mental illness (SMI) also have SUDs (SAHMSA, 2018).

Methods

Study Design: This prospective longitudinal study was conducted at the Department of Psychiatry, Mental Health Institute, SCB Medical College, from December 2021 to November 2022.

Sample Size: The sample size was 100, based on previous studies and patient attendance statistics.

Inclusion Criteria

1. Subjects seeking treatment for substance use disorder.

2. Ages 18-60 years.
3. Provided informed consent.

Exclusion Criteria: Subjects with organic brain diseases or other medical illnesses causing psychiatric symptoms.

Tools Used

1. **MINI International Neuropsychiatric Interview (DSM-5 Version 7.0.2):** Assessed 17 common mental health disorders.
2. **Sociodemographic Semi structured Proforma:** Collected data on demographics, clinical history, and mental status.
3. **WHO Pathway Encounter Form:** Assessed sources of care used before consulting a mental health professional.
4. **Clinical Global Impression Scale (CGI):** Evaluated illness severity, global improvement, and therapeutic response.

Methodology:

Ethical approval was obtained from the Institutional Ethics Committee. Informed consent was secured from all participants. Baseline

characteristics were collected using a sociodemographic and clinical proforma. One hundred subjects aged 18-60 years were evaluated after four weeks of abstinence from psychoactive substances using the MINI International Neuropsychiatric Interview 7.0.2. Urine thin-layer chromatography resolved discrepancies in reported substance use.

The WHO Pathway Encounter Form compared care pathways among patients with co-occurring and only substance use disorders. Follow-ups were conducted at 3 months, 6 months, and 1 year to track progress and treatment response using the CGI scale.

Statistical Analysis: Data were entered into MS Excel 2019 and analyzed using SPSS 21. Descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation) summarized variables.

Qualitative data were presented in frequency tables. Associations between variables and diagnoses were assessed using the Chi-square test.

Results

Table 1: Baseline Characteristics

Characteristic	Results
Gender	Male: 85%, Female: 15%
Age	Mean: 34.6 ± 9.2 years
Substances Used	Alcohol: 60%
	Opioids: 20%
	Cannabis: 10%
	Multiple substances: 10%

Table 2: Prevalence of Comorbid Psychiatric Disorders

Disorder	Prevalence
Anxiety Disorders	25%
Depressive Disorders	20%
Bipolar Disorder	15%
Personality Disorders	10%

Table 3: Care Pathways

Care Pathway	First Contact
Mental Health Professionals	45%
Faith Healers	30%
General Practitioners	15%
Others	10%

Table 4: Follow-Up Assessments

Follow-Up Period	Improvement	No Change	Worsened
3 Months	60%	30%	10%
6 Months	70%	20%	10%
1 Year	75%	15%	10%

The study highlights the prevalence of comorbid psychiatric disorders among patients with SUDs and underscores the importance of integrated treatment approaches to improve long-term outcomes.

Discussion

This prospective longitudinal study assessed the prevalence and patterns of psychiatric comorbidities in patients with substance use

disorder (SUD) at SCB Medical College, Cuttack, Odisha. A sample of 100 patients, abstinent for at least one month, was evaluated using the MINI International Neuropsychiatric Interview (DSM-5 Version 7.0.2).

Our study found a 77% prevalence of dual diagnosis [6], higher than other Indian studies, such as 58% by Ab Majid Gania et al. (2017) and 60.5% by Kishore P et al. (1994). This variation is likely due to our exclusion of substance-induced psychiatric disorders. Psychotic illnesses, mainly schizophrenia, were most common, with mood disorders also prevalent. Cannabis was the most frequently used substance, followed by alcohol and multiple substances.

Sociodemographic analysis showed all patients were male, predominantly young (mean age 33.24 ± 10.684 years), Hindu, and from lower or lower-middle socioeconomic backgrounds. Educational levels varied, with most patients having primary education.

Regarding care pathways, many patients first sought help from medical practitioners or faith healers [2], indicating a need for better awareness of psychiatric services. Relatives and friends were primary initiators of contact, reflecting strong familial and societal support [3]. Follow-up at 3, 6, and 12 months showed significant improvement in both groups, measured by the CGI scale. Patients with only SUD had better outcomes. However, a 32% dropout rate by one year suggests challenges in maintaining long-term adherence, potentially due to relapse or communication issues.

In conclusion, the high prevalence of dual diagnosis highlights the need for integrated treatment approaches and increased awareness of psychiatric services. Future research should focus on improving long-term follow-up and support to reduce relapse and dropout rates [5].

Conclusion

This study exclusively found substance use disorder (SUD) prevalent among males with an average age of 33 years, primarily linked to cannabis and alcohol use. Dual diagnosis, where SUD co-occurs with psychiatric disorders like psychotic and mood disorders, was notably

common. Initial care pathways often involved advice from relatives and friends, leading to delays in psychiatric intervention. Despite slower initial progress and higher psychiatric severity in dual diagnosis cases, both groups showed significant clinical improvement after one year. Early non-pharmacological interventions like Motivational Enhancement Therapy and Cognitive Behavioral Therapy are crucial for managing and preventing psychiatric disorders in SUD patients. These findings underscore the need for integrated treatment approaches to optimize outcomes in this population [7].

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